

Toolkit for measuring high priority, under-measured green and blue space quality in Scotland

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A companion to this report considering quality for pre-teen and teenage girls can be seen here: Conniff, A., Roberts, M., Schulz, L., Banks, E., Williams, A., & Irvine, K.N. (2026). Measuring green and blue space quality: Pre and young teenage girls in urban green and blue spaces. Report for Scottish Government. Deliverable D12 for Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing (JHI-C6-1), The James Hutton Institute, Aberdeen, Scotland. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19346873

Executive summary

Green and blue spaces are of high importance for our environment, health, society and economy. Working with stakeholders, including green and blue space managers and policy makers, we identified indicators of quality that were considered of high importance, but that were not often being used in Scotland. This toolkit is designed to signpost possible methods for measuring the benefits arising from these indicators of quality, with the aim to support development and management of high quality green and blue spaces. This supports the National Performance Indicator of access to the outdoors, and the indicators relevance to the upcoming Open Space Strategy Regulation have been identified.

The quality indicators included in this report are:

- Biodiversity
- Regulation of ecological quality
- Water quality
- Soil conservation
- Accessibility – disability
- Accessibility – site access
- Aesthetics
- Flood risk
- Social interaction

The toolkit identifies benefits (positive outcomes) and disbenefits (negative outcomes) arising from changes in the above green and blue space quality indicators. The toolkit provides a “pick and choose” approach, enabling users to first select the quality indicator in which they are interested. Secondly, they identify which benefits they are anticipating through improving the changes to quality (or that they would like to improve). Finally, they should consider available resources to select the most appropriate method. Methods are presented as:

- Low resource needs – suitable for use by everyone, particularly useful for individual green and blue space managers.
- Mid resource needs – requiring some investment in skills or time, particularly useful for managers of larger spaces, or those with wider scale decision making, and additional funding.
- High resource needs – best suited to large research projects with significant funding.

We have assessed each of the methods to support selection of the most appropriate method for the aims of the green or blue space quality assessment. For this reason, we do not present the “best” method for any benefit, because this will vary based on individual needs and resource availability. Methods are assessed based on:

- How well they transfer between sites
- How sensitive they are to change
- Whether they predict future change, or measure past change
- The comparative robustness of results
- Whether data are qualitative or quantitative
- Whether results can be presented as a monetary value

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1 Introduction

Green and blue spaces are of high importance for our environment, health, society and economy. Research has identified that it is not just the *quantity* of green and blue spaces that enable us to access these benefits, but that *quality* is often more important (Dobson *et al.*, 2019). Within Scotland access to the outdoors is a National Performance Indicator, and outdoor access has cross sectoral policy significance beyond ecology and environment, related to health, planning, education and tourism. The Planning (Scotland) Act 2019 requires planning authorities to develop Open Place Strategies, including green and blue spaces. Upcoming Open Space Strategy Regulations include requirements for:

- improving access to green infrastructure, open space and green networks
- creating successful and sustainable places
- improving health and wellbeing
- advancing equality and eliminating discrimination
- securing positive effects for biodiversity mitigation of and adaptation to climate change.

These regulations clearly demonstrate the importance of quality of green and blue spaces in delivering benefits for people, as well as their benefits to nature. As such green and blue spaces managers, policy makers and planners will need to increasingly consider how to measure and monitor green and blue space quality as experienced by people, alongside their consideration of ecological quality (Box 1).

Box 1. Definitions

Quality – Ability of space to deliver benefits or reduce disbenefits. This may include the physicality of a space (e.g., presence of smooth paths) but also includes how it is embedded in the local area (e.g., transport links), and how the space is used or perceived (e.g., how safe it feels).

Indicator – Measurable or observable green and/or blue space trait that relates to its quality.

Green and blue space – Vegetated areas and blue spaces in both urban and rural areas, including woodland, parks, farmland, paths and beaches and other aquatic environments that are publicly accessible.

Benefit – Positive outcome arising from green and/or blue space.

Disbenefit – Negative outcome arising from green and/or blue space.

Previous work in this project identified 72 potential indicators of green and blue space quality, including those reported in the literature (Roberts *et al.*, 2023) and those in use by Scottish green and blue space managers, policy makers and planners (Nicholson *et al.*, 2024). As yet, although potentially relevant to green and blue space quality, not all of these indicators are being used within Scotland. We worked with stakeholders from across Scotland, including green and blue space managers and policy makers, to identify the indicators that were of highest importance, for Scottish green and blue spaces. We further asked stakeholders to identify which of these important indicators they would like to use to measure quality in green and blue spaces, but are not currently using (Nicholson *et al.*, 2024).

We applied the lens of the Four Capitals (Advisory Group on Economic Recovery, 2020) to categorise these benefits into:

- Environment – Natural Capital: nature’s stock of natural assets.
- People – Human Dimension: health, skills, and knowledge accumulated by individuals.
- Community – Social Capital: shared understandings that enable cooperation.
- Business – Economic Capital: products of human productive activities.

In this toolkit we have selected indicators from each category within the Four Capitals framework that 1) were considered by stakeholders as most important, and 2) that they would like to use, but do not do so currently.

This research is part of Work Package 1 – Green/Blue Space Quality Indicators – within the *Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing* (JHI-C6-1) project, funded by the Scottish Government RESAS Strategic Research Programme (2022-2027). *Reciprocal Care for Nature and Wellbeing* has the aim to investigate possibilities and constraints for building capacities for such a relationship through aspects of environmental settings (type, quality), users (barriers, behaviours), mechanisms for benefit (green prescribing, outdoor learning), and investment (costs, preventative spend). This toolkit specifically addresses the environmental setting and investment components of this aim.

2 Toolkit

Green and blue space quality indicators and benefits were identified through a review of green and blue space literature (Roberts *et al.*, 2023) and two workshops held with green and blue space managers and policy makers in Scotland (Nicholson *et al.*, 2024). From this a long list of 72 indicators of quality in green and blue spaces was generated. Nine indicators were identified by green and blue space policy makers and practitioners as of high importance to them, but not currently being measured in Scottish green and blue spaces. The focus of this toolkit is on these nine indicators which include:

- Biodiversity (page 8)
- Regulation of ecological quality (page 9)
- Water quality (page 10)
- Soil Conservation (page 12)
- Accessibility (disability) (page 13)
- Accessibility (getting there) (page 14)
- Aesthetics (page 15)
- Flood risk (page 16)
- Social interaction (page 17)

The toolkit below identifies benefits (positive outcomes) and disbenefits (negative outcomes) arising from changes in the above green and blue space quality indicators. The toolkit provides a “pick and choose” approach, enabling users to first select the quality indicator in which they are interested. Secondly in the section below users identify which benefits they are anticipating through improving the changes to quality (or that they would like to improve). Finally, users consider available resources to select the most appropriate method, classified as:

- Low – Time and skills requirements can be small, and most people could be expected to carry out this method with limited self-training. If primary data collection (i.e., collection of data by the user) is required this will not be complicated to collect. These methods are suitable for all and may be particularly useful for green and blue space managers with limited resources.
- ● Mid – Some investment in time and skills will be required, likely involving some external training if skills are not already present. If primary data is to be collected this will likely be more involved. These methods would be suitable for green and blue space managers with funding available for monitoring quality, or planners and managers of larger areas.
- ● ● High – Investment of time and skills development will be needed, with involvement of research institutions. These methods would be suitable for researchers or regional or national scale managers, planners or policy makers with significant funding to invest in research.

In addition to providing details of the appropriate methods we also identify which of the Open Space Standard Regulation aims each quality indicator and (dis)benefit may be relevant for:

Icon	Aim
	Improving access to green infrastructure, open space and green networks
	Creating successful and sustainable places
	Improving health and wellbeing
	Advancing equality and eliminating discrimination
	Securing positive effects for biodiversity mitigation of and adaptation to climate change.

We then present details of each method. We have assessed each of the methods based on attributes which may influence whether and where they may be best suited to be used. This assessment will support selection of the most appropriate method for the aims of the green or blue space quality assessment. For this reason, we do not present the “best” method for any benefit, because this will vary based on individual needs and resource availability. Methods are assessed based on:

- **Transferability** – Potential for results of the method implemented in one location to be applicable in a different location. Transferability is particularly relevant if you want to be able to apply results over a large area, or to multiple sites.
- **Resources** – Amount of resources needed to carry out the method. Given that this may vary between specific situations we have estimated the minimum resources required. Resource needs are organised into data required, time required, and skills of those carrying out the work. The amount of resources available will dictate whether a particular method is feasible to implement. Decisions should consider more than just the monetary resources but also the human resources of time and skills available.
- **Sensitivity** – Ability of the method to detect small changes in quality. A more sensitive method will detect changes more quickly, or changes that happen on a smaller scale. This is important when considering the scale of change that may be expected when improving quality.
- **Predictive or retrospective** – Can the method be applied before a change is made to a space, to forecast what the impact of change may be (predictive) or is it applied afterwards to measure the impact of a change? Selecting the correct method is important to achieve goals of measurement.
- **Quality** – Although all methods presented in this toolkit are considered to produce robust results, the quality may vary from the “gold standard” methods, which have associated high resource needs, to those with lower resource needs, which produce less high quality results, but are still able to improve knowledge about green and blue space quality. The ranking applied here is intended to allow users to trade-off other needs and choose the most high quality approach possible for their area of interest.
- **Qualitative/quantitative** – Methods may report numerical data, or data based on text, such as outcomes from interview or workshops. Some methods may report both types of data. Identifying which is more appropriate will require considering what is going to be done with the data once collected.

- £ – Monetary methods report, or can report, outcomes in monetary terms (e.g., costs, value). This can be important for cost-benefit analysis in particular.

2.1 Benefits and disbenefits

We present below the potential benefits and disbenefits from improving quality indicators, including where they fall into the Open Space Strategy aims and resources required. For full details see “Toolkit” section.

2.1.1 Biodiversity

Biodiversity includes all of living things, including plants, and animals, but also small or microscopic organisms such as fungi or bacteria. Biodiversity in particular refers to the different types of organisms, as well as the number of each that can be found. Improving biodiversity is often a key tenant of creating or maintaining green and blue spaces, particularly for above ground plants and animals. Biodiversity benefits included within the toolkit include:

2.1.1.1 [Opportunities to observe nature](#)

This might include opportunities to view rare or iconic species, but can also include local bird watching, for example. Observation of nature has been recorded as having many beneficial impacts on, for example, health and wellbeing, but is also considered to be a benefit of biodiversity in and of itself. Opportunities to observe nature can be measured through:

- Travel cost** (page 23) ●
- Semi-structured interviews** (page 31) ●
- Multiple choice surveys** (page 38) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Hedonic pricing** (page 22) ●●
- Open interviews** (page 30) ●●
- In activity (walking) interviews** (page 32) ●●
- Choice experiment** (page 27) ●●●

2.1.1.2 [Physical health](#)

Physical health benefits include those to physical fitness as well as reductions in disease or chronic conditions, or improvements in outcomes. These can be measured through:

- Semi-structured interviews** (page 31) ●
- Health self-report** (page 36) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Value of statistical life** (page 28) ●●
- Open interviews** (page 30) ●●
- In activity (walking) interviews** (page 32) ●●
- Systematic literature review** (page 34) ●●
- Qualitative surveys** (page 37) ●●
- Contingent valuation** (Page 25) ●●●
- Choice experiment** (page 27) ●●●

2.1.1.3 Wellbeing

Benefits to wellbeing include reductions in mental health disorders, in either number, length or severity. Wellbeing also includes everyday wellbeing, such as mood, stress or life satisfaction. This can be measured using the methods:

- Semi-structured interviews** (page 31) ●
- Health self-report** (page 36) ●
- Multiple choice surveys** (page 38) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Population modelling** (page 29) ● ●
- Open interviews** (page 30) ● ●
- In activity (walking) interviews** (page 32) ● ●
- Choice experiment** (page 27) ● ● ●
- Ethnographic interviews** (page 33) ● ● ●

2.1.1.4 Recreation

Recreation includes both organised and informal recreation, which may be active (e.g., going for a walk) or sedentary (e.g., a picnic), and can be in groups or alone. The benefits of recreation can be measured through:

- Travel cost** (page 23) ●
- Multiple choice surveys** (page 38) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Hedonic pricing** (page 22) ● ●
- Contingent behaviour** (page 26) ● ● ●
- Choice experiment** (page 27) ● ● ●

2.1.2 Regulation of ecological quality

Green and blue spaces are linked to wider ecological networks. These ecological networks work in balance with each other, impacting ecological functioning beyond individual components of a space. For example, riparian woodlands may reduce soil erosion which maintains water quality, with consequences for downstream fishes. Benefits included in the toolkit are:

2.1.2.1 Drinking water

Drinking water is gained through abstraction from rivers or reservoirs and must be treated before use. Benefits of cleaner drinking water can be assessed using the methods:

- Direct estimation** (page 19) ●
- Gross margin loss** (page 21) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Damage curves** (page 20) ● ● ●
- Choice experiment** (page 27) ● ● ●

2.1.2.2 Reduced flood damage costs

Green and blue spaces can mitigate flooding, leading to reduced damages. The benefits of this can be measured through:

- Direct estimation** (page 19) ●
- Gross margin loss** (page 21) ●

- Semi-structured interviews** (page 31) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Open interviews** (page 30) ●●
- Damage curves** (page 20) ●●●
- Contingent valuation** (Page 25) ●●●●

2.1.2.3 [Loss of crops/revenue](#)

Changes to environment, including flooding, can negatively impact crops through crop losses, or increased costs of production. These impacts can be measured through:

- Gross margin loss** (page 21) ●
- Semi-structured interviews** (page 31) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Open interviews** (page 30) ●●

2.1.2.4 [Transport](#)

Transport routes through and around green and blue spaces can be impacted by events such as flooding, landslides or vegetation. These impacts can be measured through:

- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Wage rate substitution** (page 24) ●●●
- Choice experiment** (page 27) ●●●

2.1.3 [Water quality](#)

Water quality can include water found within the green or blue space, as well as water that might be extracted for drinking or other uses (e.g., agriculture). Water quality may directly impact users (e.g., illness from coming into contact with poor quality water) or may indirectly impact through for example sight or smell.

2.1.3.1 [Physical health](#)

Physical health benefits include those to physical fitness as well as reductions in disease or chronic conditions, or improvements in outcomes. These can be measured through:

- Semi-structured interviews** (page 31) ●
- Health self-report** (page 36) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Value of statistical life** (page 28) ●●
- Open interviews** (page 30) ●●
- In activity (walking) interviews** (page 32) ●●
- Systematic literature review** (page 34) ●●
- Qualitative surveys** (page 37) ●●
- Contingent valuation** (Page 25) ●●●
- Choice experiment** (page 27) ●●●

2.1.3.2 [Wellbeing](#)

Benefits to wellbeing include reductions in mental health disorders, in either number, length or severity. Wellbeing also includes everyday wellbeing, such as mood, stress or life satisfaction. This can be measured using the methods:

- Semi-structured interviews** (page 31) ●
- Health self-report** (page 36) ●

- Multiple choice surveys** (page 38) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Population modelling** (page 29) ●●
- Open interviews** (page 30) ●●
- In activity (walking) interviews** (page 32) ●●
- Choice experiment** (page 27) ●●●
- Ethnographic interviews** (page 33) ●●●

2.1.3.3 [Food](#)

Benefits from food are not limited to nutrition, they also include connections to place, locality of food and links to growing and farming.

- Semi-structured interviews** (page 31) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Open interviews** (page 30) ●●
- In activity (walking) interviews** (page 32) ●●
- Diary** (page 39) ●●
- Ethnographic interviews** (page 33) ●●●

2.1.3.4 [Recreation](#)

Recreation includes both organised and informal recreation, which may be active (e.g., going for a walk) or sedentary (e.g., a picnic), and can be in groups or alone. The benefits of recreation can be measured through:

- Travel cost** (page 23) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Multiple choice surveys** (page 38) ●
- Hedonic pricing** (page 22) ●●
- Contingent behaviour** (page 26) ●●●
- Choice experiment** (page 27) ●●●

2.1.3.5 [Tourism](#)

Tourism includes both long visits and day trips and is differentiated from recreation because these involve non-local visitors, and typically less regular trips, although repeat visits may be included. The benefits can be measured through:

- Travel cost** (page 23) ●
- Semi-structured interviews** (page 31) ●
- Multiple choice surveys** (page 38) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Hedonic pricing** (page 22) ●●
- Open interviews** (page 30) ●●
- In activity (walking) interviews** (page 32) ●●
- Contingent valuation** (Page 25) ●●●
- Contingent behaviour** (page 26) ●●●
- Choice experiment** (page 27) ●●●

2.1.3.6 [Drinking water](#)

Drinking water is gained through abstraction from rivers or reservoirs and must be treated before use. Benefits of cleaner drinking water can be assessed using the methods:

- Direct estimation** (page 19) ●
- Gross margin loss** (page 21) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●

Damage curves (page 20) ●●●

Choice experiment (page 27) ●●●

2.1.3.7 [Transport](#)

Transport routes through and around green and blue spaces can be impacted by events such as flooding, landslides or vegetation. These impacts can be measured through:

Benefit transfer (page 35) ●

Wage rate substitution (page 24) ●●●

Choice experiment (page 27) ●●●

2.1.4 [Soil Conservation](#)

Soil conservation can impact across uses of green and blue spaces. Soil erosion can reduce physical access and visual appeal, lead to de-stabilisation and raise safety concerns, as well as impacting things such as water quality or depth.

2.1.4.1 [Reduced flood damage costs](#)

Green and blue spaces can mitigate flooding, leading to reduced damages. The benefits of this can be measured through:

Direct estimation (page 19) ●

Gross margin loss (page 21) ●

Semi-structured interviews (page 31) ●

Benefit transfer (page 35) ●

Open interviews (page 30) ●●

Damage curves (page 20) ●●●

Contingent valuation (Page 25) ●●●

2.1.4.2 [Burial sites](#)

Stable long-term burial sites are important practically for safe storage of human remains, but also for the cultural and spiritual connections they facilitate. Their benefits can be measured through:

Semi-structured interviews (page 31) ●

Benefit transfer (page 35) ●

Hedonic pricing (page 22) ●●

Open interviews (page 30) ●●

Focus groups (page 40) ●●

2.1.4.3 [Food](#)

Benefits from food are not limited to nutrition, they also include connections to place, locality of food and links to growing and farming.

Semi-structured interviews (page 31) ●

Benefit transfer (page 35) ●

Open interviews (page 30) ●●

In activity (walking) interviews (page 32) ●●

Diary (page 39) ●●

Ethnographic interviews (page 33) ●●●

2.1.5 Accessibility (disability)

Accessibility for disability can include things such as physical accessibility (e.g., wide smooth paths, ramps) as well as additional facilities such as benches or toilets, or maps of places and clear plans for events, to support neurodiverse users. Such accessibility increases potential for access to benefits provided by other aspects of green and blue spaces. We use the social model of disability, recognising that people are disabled by barriers in society and space, not by individual impairment (Disability Rights UK, 2025).

2.1.5.1 Physical health

Physical health benefits include those to physical fitness as well as reductions in disease or chronic conditions, or improvements in outcomes. These can be measured through:

- Semi-structured interviews** (page 31) ●
- Health self-report** (page 36) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Value of statistical life** (page 28) ●●
- Open interviews** (page 30) ●●
- In activity (walking) interviews** (page 32) ●●
- Systematic literature review** (page 34) ●●
- Qualitative surveys** (page 37) ●●
- Contingent valuation** (Page 25) ●●●
- Choice experiment** (page 27) ●●●

2.1.5.2 Wellbeing

Benefits to wellbeing include reductions in mental health disorders, in either number, length or severity. Wellbeing also includes everyday wellbeing, such as mood, stress or life satisfaction.

This can be measured using the methods:

- Semi-structured interviews** (page 31) ●
- Health self-report** (page 36) ●
- Multiple choice surveys** (page 38) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Population modelling** (page 29) ●●
- Open interviews** (page 30) ●●
- In activity (walking) interviews** (page 32) ●●
- Choice experiment** (page 27) ●●●
- Ethnographic interviews** (page 33) ●●●

2.1.5.3 Social interaction

Social interaction includes the facilitation of social meeting, ideally prolonged or repeated. This can be measured through:

- Semi-structured interviews** (page 31) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Open interviews** (page 30) ●●
- In activity (walking) interviews** (page 32) ●●
- Observation** (page 41) ●●
- Ethnographic interviews** (page 33) ●●●

2.1.5.4 [Transport](#)

Transport routes through and around green and blue spaces can be impacted by events such as flooding, landslides or vegetation. These impacts can be measured through:

- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Wage rate substitution** (page 24) ●●●
- Choice experiment** (page 27) ●●●

2.1.6 [Accessibility \(getting there\)](#)

Getting to the site impacts who is able to access the benefits of visiting green and blue spaces. Sites which can be accessed via safe, well-lit walking paths or public transport will be more open to a wider variety of visitors.

2.1.6.1 [Physical health](#)

Physical health benefits include those to physical fitness as well as reductions in disease or chronic conditions, or improvements in outcomes. These can be measured through:

- Semi-structured interviews** (page 31) ●
- Health self-report** (page 36) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Value of statistical life** (page 28) ●●
- Open interviews** (page 30) ●●
- In activity (walking) interviews** (page 32) ●●
- Systematic literature review** (page 34) ●●
- Qualitative surveys** (page 37) ●●
- Contingent valuation** (Page 25) ●●●
- Choice experiment** (page 27) ●●●

2.1.6.2 [Wellbeing](#)

Benefits to wellbeing include reductions in mental health disorders, in either number, length or severity. Wellbeing also includes everyday wellbeing, such as mood, stress or life satisfaction.

This can be measured using the methods:

- Semi-structured interviews** (page 31) ●
- Health self-report** (page 36) ●
- Multiple choice surveys** (page 38) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Population modelling** (page 29) ●●
- Open interviews** (page 30) ●●
- In activity (walking) interviews** (page 32) ●●
- Choice experiment** (page 27) ●●●
- Ethnographic interviews** (page 33) ●●●

2.1.6.3 [Reduce social deprivation](#)

Social deprivation refers to low access to the benefits of society. Although green and blue spaces cannot combat this, they can have a role to play in reduction. This can be measured through:

- Population modelling** (page 29) ●●

2.1.6.4 [Transport](#)

Transport routes through and around green and blue spaces can be impacted by events such as flooding, landslides or vegetation. These impacts can be measured through:

- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Wage rate substitution** (page 24) ● ● ●
- Choice experiment** (page 27) ● ● ●

2.1.6.5 [Social interaction](#)

Social interaction includes the facilitation of social meeting, ideally prolonged or repeated. This can be measured through:

- Semi-structured interviews** (page 31) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Open interviews** (page 30) ● ●
- In activity (walking) interviews** (page 32) ● ●
- Observation** (page 41) ● ●
- Ethnographic interviews** (page 33) ● ● ●

2.1.7 [Aesthetics](#)

The visual look of a green or blue space can impact users' enjoyment. Aesthetics may relate to the natural features, such as the view or colour of flowers, but can also include negative aspects, such as bordering busy roads or graffiti.

2.1.7.1 [Wellbeing](#)

Benefits to wellbeing include reductions in mental health disorders, in either number, length or severity. Wellbeing also includes everyday wellbeing, such as mood, stress or life satisfaction. This can be measured using the methods:

- Semi-structured interviews** (page 31) ●
- Health self-report** (page 36) ●
- Multiple choice surveys** (page 38) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Population modelling** (page 29) ● ●
- Open interviews** (page 30) ● ●
- In activity (walking) interviews** (page 32) ● ●
- Choice experiment** (page 27) ● ● ●
- Ethnographic interviews** (page 33) ● ● ●

2.1.7.2 [Reduce social deprivation](#)

Social deprivation refers to low access to the benefits of society. Although green and blue spaces cannot combat this, they can have a role to play in reduction. This can be measured through:

- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Population modelling** (page 29) ● ●

2.1.8 Flood risk

Flood risk can impact the functioning and safety of the green or blue space for users, as well as their access. Further, it may impact the ability of the green and blue spaces to deliver other benefits, such as improved water quality, or impact aesthetics even after the flood event has passed.

2.1.8.1 [Increase land value](#)

Land value can be impacted by surrounding environment, and can be measured through:

Benefit transfer (page 35) ●

Hedonic pricing (page 22) ●●

2.1.8.2 [Reduced flood damage costs](#)

Green and blue spaces can mitigate flooding, leading to reduced damages. The benefits of this can be measured through:

Direct estimation (page 19) ●

Gross margin loss (page 21) ●

Semi-structured interviews (page 31) ●

Benefit transfer (page 35) ●

Open interviews (page 30) ●●

Damage curves (page 20) ●●●

Contingent valuation (Page 25) ●●●●

2.1.8.3 [Loss of crops/revenue](#)

Changes to environment, including flooding, can negatively impact crops through crop losses, or increased costs of production. These impacts can be measured through:

Gross margin loss (page 21) ●

Semi-structured interviews (page 31) ●

Benefit transfer (page 35) ●

Open interviews (page 30) ●●

2.1.8.4 [Recreation](#)

Recreation includes both organised and informal recreation, which may be active (e.g., going for a walk) or sedentary (e.g., a picnic), and can be in groups or alone. The benefits of recreation can be measured through:

Travel cost (page 23) ●

Multiple choice surveys (page 38) ●

Benefit transfer (page 35) ●

Hedonic pricing (page 22) ●●

Contingent behaviour (page 26) ●●●●

Choice experiment (page 27) ●●●●

2.1.8.5 [Drinking water](#)

Drinking water is gained through abstraction from rivers or reservoirs and must be treated before use. Benefits of cleaner drinking water can be assessed using the methods:

Direct estimation (page 19) ●

Gross margin loss (page 21) ●

Benefit transfer (page 35) ●

Damage curves (page 20) ●●●●

Choice experiment (page 27) ● ● ●

2.1.9 Social interaction

Green and blue spaces can be designed to facilitate social interaction, through the design of their paths, presence of facilities such as cafes, or layout of benches. Additionally, social interaction may be encouraged through activities or other social interventions happening within the green or blue space.

2.1.9.1 [Physical health](#)

Physical health benefits include those to physical fitness as well as reductions in disease or chronic conditions, or improvements in outcomes. These can be measured through:

- Semi-structured interviews** (page 31) ●
- Health self-report** (page 36) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Value of statistical life** (page 28) ● ●
- Open interviews** (page 30) ● ●
- In activity (walking) interviews** (page 32) ● ●
- Systematic literature review** (page 34) ● ●
- Qualitative surveys** (page 37) ● ●
- Contingent valuation** (Page 25) ● ● ●
- Choice experiment** (page 27) ● ● ●

2.1.9.2 [Wellbeing](#)

Benefits to wellbeing include reductions in mental health disorders, in either number, length or severity. Wellbeing also includes everyday wellbeing, such as mood, stress or life satisfaction.

This can be measured using the methods:

- Semi-structured interviews** (page 31) ●
- Health self-report** (page 36) ●
- Multiple choice surveys** (page 38) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Population modelling** (page 29) ● ●
- Open interviews** (page 30) ● ●
- In activity (walking) interviews** (page 32) ● ●
- Choice experiment** (page 27) ● ● ●
- Ethnographic interviews** (page 33) ● ● ●

2.1.9.3 [Imaginative and creative play for children](#)

Children require dedicated places for play, with Play Sufficiency a key component of Open Space Strategies. This can be measured through:

- Semi-structured interviews** (page 31) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Open interviews** (page 30) ● ●
- In activity (walking) interviews** (page 32) ● ●
- Focus groups** (page 40) ● ●
- Observation** (page 41) ● ●

2.1.9.4 [Sense of community](#)

This includes not just the interaction people have between themselves but extends to people's connection to place and feelings of belonging. These can be measured through:

- Semi-structured interviews** (page 31) ●
- Multiple choice surveys** (page 38) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Open interviews** (page 30) ● ●
- In activity (walking) interviews** (page 32) ● ●
- Focus groups** (page 40) ● ●
- Observation** (page 41) ● ●
- Ethnographic interviews** (page 33) ● ● ●

2.1.9.5 [Safety](#)

Safe spaces require not just physically safe environment but also feeling of safety due to other people.

- Semi-structured interviews** (page 31) ●
- Multiple choice surveys** (page 38) ●
- Benefit transfer** (page 35) ●
- Open interviews** (page 30) ● ●
- In activity (walking) interviews** (page 32) ● ●
- Focus groups** (page 40) ● ●
- Choice experiment** (page 27) ● ● ●

Avoided costs	Resources: Low ●		
Direct estimation	Data: Primary (secondary possible)	Time: Low	Skills: Low
<p>Overview</p> <p>This method compares costs before and after a change in quality. The measure of the benefit arising from the change in quality is related to the reduction in costs. Care must be taken to ensure that the change in cost can be attributed to the intervention (i.e., nothing else has changed which may impact the costs measured).</p> <p>Costs can often be collected via secondary data (e.g., costs of water cleaning or insurance claims for flooding), or primary data, where individuals or businesses are surveyed for their costs. Where events are sporadic (e.g., floods) data may be collected on the previous costs of the event, and used to estimate how much money may be saved through reductions in future events.</p>	Transferability	High	
	Sensitivity	Low	
	Predictive or retrospective?	Both	
	Quality	High	
	Qualitative or quantitative?	Quant	
	Monetary?	Yes	
	<p>Quality</p> <p>This is a well-established method and uses observed costs data. Care must be taken that the cost reductions can be linked to the intervention, and not to other changes over the same time period.</p>	<p>Predictive or retrospective</p> <p>Avoided costs can be used predictively where models can be created to estimate the impact of the intervention, linked to current or industry average costs. However, damage curves may be a more appropriate method in this case. This is more resource intensive than retrospective use of avoided costs, where costs before and after the intervention can be directly measured.</p>	
<p>Resources</p> <p>Primary data is likely to have to be collected, although in some cases secondary data may be available. Collection of data and cleaning to enable comparison of data is likely to be the most time consuming element of the work.</p> <p>Analysis is straightforward where secondary data is available, and the link to changes in costs is clear. Some skills in regression analysis required.</p>	<p>What is it useful for, and where has it been applied?</p> <p>Direct estimation is a suitable measure of green or blue space quality when things that are directly brought and sold are impacted. To measure costs of flooding Werritty <i>et. al.</i> (2007) and Owusu <i>et. al.</i> (2015) surveyed previously flooded households to estimate costs of past floods. Such information can then be used to estimate the benefit of avoided future events.</p> <p>Direct estimation can also be used where public spending is increased or reduced. This has previously been used to measure the benefits of planting trees in a watershed to reduce public spending on drinking water cleaning (Postel and Thompson, 2005).</p>		
<p>Sensitivity</p> <p>Time taken for the change in direct costs estimated will depend on the strength of the link between intervention and outcome measured. It is likely, however, that changes would need to occur over a medium to large area to see impacts on market prices or public spending.</p>			
<p>Transferability</p> <p>Values estimated can be readily transferred to similar areas, particularly where large areas and average costs have been used. Care should be taken if transferring values to smaller entities (e.g., single businesses), because other factors may be more influential for costs at this resolution.</p>			

Avoided costs	Resources: Mid ●●●		
Damage curves	Data: Primary (secondary possible)	Time: Mid	Skills: High
<p>Overview</p> <p>Damage curves model the expected impacts of future events (e.g., flooding), and the costs which could be expected to be incurred. Damage curves require estimation of the area over which an impact would be felt (e.g., flood area), the goods or property of interest that would be expected to be impacted (e.g., vehicles), the value of these goods (e.g., market price), and the anticipated extent of damage (e.g., 50% loss of value, total loss of value). The value of an improvement can then be estimated as the avoidance of paying these damage costs.</p>	Transferability	High	
	Sensitivity	Mid	
	Predictive or retrospective?	P	
	Quality	High	
	Qualitative or quantitative?	Quant	
	Monetary?	Yes	
<p>Quality</p> <p>Well established and reliant on observed costs data. Care must be taken that the cost reductions can be linked to the intervention.</p>	<p>Predictive or retrospective</p> <p>Damage curves predict future damages, and so cannot be used retrospectively. Direct estimation would be more appropriate for retrospective studies.</p>		
<p>Resources</p> <p>Large amounts of primary data collection needed, and as such the time required to carry out the research is also significant. Modelling needs can be substantial.</p>			
<p>Sensitivity</p> <p>Level of sensitivity will depend on the strength of the link between the intervention and the outcome measured. Direct links will be readily detected, however where indirect links are studied the consequences of other things impacting the outcome will reduce sensitivity.</p>	<p>What is it useful for, and where has it been applied?</p> <p>Damage curves are best applied where the change in the extent of the expected event (e.g., flood area) is well understood. They have been used by Martinez-Gomariz <i>et. al.</i> (2019) to estimate the direct damage to vehicles as a result of flooding.</p>		
<p>Transferability</p> <p>Values estimated can be transferred to similar areas, however, this will perform best where the transfer is of average values between large areas, rather than single green or blue spaces.</p>			

Avoided costs	Resources: Low ●		
Gross margin loss	Data: Primary (secondary possible)	Time: Low	Skills: Low
Overview Gross margin loss can be used to calculate the loss in profit experienced as a result of an event. This is done by comparing the profits realised with the predicted profits, minus any savings through reduced effort (e.g., no harvesting).	Transferability		High
	Sensitivity		Low
	Predictive or retrospective?		R
	Quality		High
	Qualitative or quantitative?		Quant
	Monetary?		Yes
Quality Gross margin loss is based on real impacts. Quality will be higher where data from the site is collected, as opposed to use of average values.	Predictive or retrospective Gross margin loss is based on recorded loss, so typically retrospective. Models and transferred values may be applied to predict losses, however damage curves may be more appropriate.		
	Resources Primary data collection often needed to estimate impacts, though secondary data may be available in specific cases. All data is part of everyday business accounting, and so additional time needed to collect data is low. Limited modelling needed beyond what is normally carried out as part of everyday business accounting.		
Sensitivity Where the link to production is direct gross margin loss will be very sensitive in identifying impacts. More indirect connections may reduce sensitivity.	What is it useful for, and where has it been applied? Gross margin loss is best used when the benefit of improving green or blue space quality impacts on a direct market good (i.e., something that is sold directly as is). It is most readily applied to businesses. This has been demonstrated by Bremond <i>et al</i> (2013) in estimating value of crop losses due to flooding.		
Transferability High between areas producing similar goods with similar green or blue spaces. Per ha costs are often applied, and are easily transferred..			

Revealed Preferences	Resources: Mid ●●		
Hedonic pricing	Data: Secondary	Time: Low	Skills: High
<p>Overview</p> <p>Hedonic pricing uses the relationship between the variation in prices for non-movable goods (e.g., housing), and other variation in the environment (e.g., green space). If prices are higher closer to a green or blue space of particular quality, where all other things are kept equal, then this additional benefit can be ascribed to the green or blue space quality. These relationships can be estimated either via regression modelling with spatial variation (e.g., variation in access to play areas), or differences in prices pre and post-intervention (e.g., establishment of new play area).</p> <p>Whether variation is measured in space or in time the scale of measurement needs to be large to observe any difference (i.e., over a large area, or a long timescale). This is particularly the case where house prices are used, because house sales are relatively infrequent. Care must also be taken to account for other things that may impact prices (e.g., schools, supermarkets, house size).</p>	Transferability	Mid	
	Sensitivity	Low	
	Predictive or retrospective?	R	
	Quality	High	
	Qualitative or quantitative?	Quant	
	Monetary?	Yes	
		<p>Predictive or retrospective</p> <p>Relying on market sales hedonic pricing can only be used for retrospective valuation.</p>	
<p>Quality</p> <p>The method is well established and relies in real costs data. However, care must be taken to ensure that all variable impacting price are incorporated.</p>	<p>What is it useful for, and where has it been applied?</p> <p>Hedonic pricing is best used for large changes, over long time periods and large areas. Hedonic prices are most often in relation to house prices, such as the value of the creation of a new green space for recreation and nature observation opportunities, estimated through impact on house prices by Iftekhhar <i>et. al.</i> (2022). In this study the authors combined hedonic pricing results with stated preference models. Land prices (Zhang <i>et al.</i>, 2012, 2020) or holiday rental prices (de Jonge, 2021) can also be used. Because holiday rental prices may change over a shorter time period these can also be used to estimate change more quickly. Hedonic pricing has also been used to estimate the value of burial plots by Faye and Channac (2017) and Canofari <i>et. al.</i> (2017).</p>		
<p>Resources</p> <p>Typically relies on publicly available secondary data, and relatively short time requirements. However, GIS skills are required, and extensive modelling needed.</p>			
<p>Sensitivity</p> <p>Due to relying on market prices, often for goods which are not sold frequently (e.g., houses), the time taken for impacts of change to be observed is high. Because prices are impacted by many additional variables (e.g., schools, lending rates, transport) hedonic pricing will only be able to detect impacts of large changes.</p>			
<p>Transferability</p> <p>Values are transferable but both the green or blue space qualities and the other variables impacting price need to be comparable.</p>			

Revealed Preferences	Resources: Low ●		
Travel cost	Data: Primary	Time: Low	Skills: Low
<p>Overview</p> <p>Travel cost estimates the benefit a location gives people based on the amount it costs them to visit. This is typically gained through survey or interview of visitors to a site, either during the visit or by phone, post or online on their return. Cost estimates can be gained either through directly asking for costs, or estimated from starting location and mode of transport. In addition to travel cost accommodation can also be included, if appropriate.</p> <p>Travel cost can be used to estimate the value of a single site (e.g., national park). Comparisons between travel costs to different sites (e.g., parks with or without play equipment) can enable estimation of the value of particular attributes of a space. Care must be taken to account for other difference between sites, and their access options.</p>	Transferability	Mid	
	Sensitivity	Mid	
	Predictive or retrospective?	R	
	Quality	High	
	Qualitative or quantitative?	Quant	
	Monetary?	Yes	
		<p>Predictive or retrospective</p> <p>Travel cost is typically retrospective, looking at changes to travel following intervention. For predictive estimates it may be combined with contingent behaviour method.</p>	
Quality	<p>What is it useful for, and where has it been applied?</p> <p>Travel cost can be used to estimate benefits across multiple sites, with variation in benefit gained between sites giving insight into the benefit of varied quality sites. An extensive travel cost study was carried out by Heagney <i>et. al.</i> (2019), in which a national level phone survey of visits to national parks in New South Wales, Australia, was used to estimate value of the national park network. This study also included non-users. A similar study, albeit on a smaller scale, was carried out by Borger <i>et. al.</i> (2021). Here both tourism and recreation value was estimated via an online survey of visitors to inland water.</p>		
Well established method based on real behaviour.			
Resources	<p>Primary data collection is required, with large sample sizes, though this can be achieved through online survey if the population of users can be reached. Modelling is also complex, needing to account for alternative impacts on travel costs.</p>		
Sensitivity	<p>Areas large enough to impact visitor numbers are required to be changed for an impact to be observed. Speed of change identified will also depend on the availability of information to visitors of the change, and so a time lag may be observed.</p>		
Transferability	<p>Transferable between similar areas, transport options, and user populations.</p>		

Revealed Preferences	Resources: Mid ●●		
Wage rate substitution	Data: Primary (secondary possible)	Time: Mid	Skills: Mid
<p>Overview</p> <p>Wage rate substitution estimates value based on the wages that could have been earned the time spent on the activity (e.g., birdwatching) was spent working. This method is often combined with travel time, to estimate the cost of time as well as the mode of transport, but can be used for any activity that takes time. Value can be a percentage of wage, median wage, or full recorded wage. An individuals value often depends on preferences for type of travel, proportion of time spent moving vs waiting, and whether time is spent for work or leisure.</p>	Transferability	Mid	
	Sensitivity	Mid	
	Predictive or retrospective?	R	
	Quality	Mid	
	Qualitative or quantitative?	Quant	
	Monetary?	Yes	
	Predictive or retrospective	This method measures time spent at a site following change, and so can only be used retrospectively. For predictive use wage rate substitution can be combined with contingent behaviour models.	
<p>Quality</p> <p>Well established and relies on observed behaviour. However, valuation relies on the assumption of free choice over how to spend time, and can value higher paid individuals' time higher than lower paid individuals if real wages are used, risking perpetuating inequality.</p>	<p>What is it useful for, and where has it been applied?</p> <p>Wage rate substitution is suitable for spaces that visitors spend time in, similar to travel cost models. A detailed example of wage rate substitution in travel cost models is given in Small (2012).</p>		
<p>Resources</p> <p>Data requirements vary, but most accurate results will be achieved through use of primary collection of real wage data. Alternatively, published averages may be used. Modelling may be complex.</p>			
<p>Sensitivity</p> <p>The area over which change must occur needs to be large enough to impact time spent at a site, and so are likely to be over larger areas. As with travel cost, time for impact to be measured may also depend on how well communicated the change is to infrequent visitors.</p>			
<p>Transferability</p> <p>Transferable between similar areas, transport options, and user populations.</p>			

Stated Preferences	Resources: High ●●●			
Contingent valuation	Data: Primary	Time: High	Skills: High	
<p>Overview Contingent valuation asks populations for their willingness to pay for a good (e.g., via entrance fee or increased tax) based on a hypothetical change to the good (e.g., installation of lighting). Because contingent valuation relies on hypothetical changes care must be taken to ensure that respondents understand well the change being proposed, and are inclined to state their true willingness to pay.</p> <p>Surveys are carried out either on site with users (e.g., at a park) or remotely via telephone, post, or online, where both users and non-users may be targeted. Typically, as well as the valuation exercise surveys will include questions relating to use of the site, preferences towards the environment, and demographics, among others. Contingent valuation is often used to estimate value of larger scale changes (e.g., national or regional level), and can be used at a population level. Due to large sample sizes needed it is usually not appropriate at the very local scale.</p>	Transferability	Mid		
	Sensitivity	High		
	Predictive or retrospective?	P		
	Quality	Mid		
	Qualitative or quantitative?	Quant		
	Monetary?	Yes		
	Predictive or retrospective	Contingent valuation is predictive in valuing hypothetical future scenarios.		
	What is it useful for, and where has it been applied?	Due to large sample sizes needed contingent valuation is most suitable for large scale changes. However, smaller changes may be measured in high traffic areas. Contingent valuation can only be used to measure changes that are observable in some way to users. It is often applied to value changes in park area. For example, benefit of lake-side recreation were measured in relation to improvements in path quality, lakeside access, and views, with payment options given between 50p and £120 (McDougall et al., 2020).		
	Quality	Well established and relies on observed behaviour. However, valuation relies on the assumption of free choice over how to spend time, and can value higher paid individuals' time higher than lower paid individuals if real wages are used, risking perpetuating inequality.		
	Resources	Contingent valuation has high resource needs, including collection of large amounts of primary data. Specialised skill sets are needed in design and analysis of the survey, and time requirements are also likely to be significant.		
Sensitivity	The is potential to detect small changes, though this will depend on a carefully created survey instrument and well-designed scenarios.			
Transferability	Due to the hypothetical nature of the valuation some transferability is possible, however, great care must be taken to ensure that populations are the same in the transfer site, and that relationships to the site can be expected to be similar.			

Stated Preferences	Resources: High ●●●		
Contingent behaviour	Data: Primary	Time: High	Skills: High
Overview Contingent behaviour is very similar to contingent valuation, however instead of hypothetical payments, respondents are asked how their behaviour may change in relation to hypothetical changes. Unlike contingent valuation contingent behaviour is only normally carried out with users, and so more often is carried out on site. The exception to this may be if a new development was proposed, where potential users may be surveyed.	Transferability	Mid	
	Sensitivity	High	
	Predictive or retrospective?	P	
	Quality	Mid	
	Qualitative or quantitative?	Quant	
	Monetary?	Yes	
	Predictive or retrospective Contingent behaviour is predictive in valuing hypothetical future scenarios.		
Quality Contingent behaviour is built on contingent valuation, which is a well-established method. However, contingent behaviour has received less attention than contingent valuation, and so care must be taken in design and interpretation of results.	What is it useful for, and where has it been applied? Contingent behaviour is used less frequently than valuation, however, has still been used to understand quality of green and blue spaces. The survey, carried out online, asked whether respondents would make more or fewer trips to a site if the water quality increased or decreased. This data was linked to travel cost data collected at the same time to estimate a value (Börger <i>et al.</i> , 2021).		
Resources Resource needs are equivalent to that of contingent valuation, with high data and skills required, and significant time.			
Sensitivity There is potential to detect small changes, though this will depend on a carefully created survey instrument and well-designed scenarios.			
Transferability Unlike contingent valuation, transferability is likely to be low, with significant care needed to match both area and user population.			

Stated Preferences	Resources: High ● ● ●		
Choice experiment	Data: Primary	Time: High	Skills: High
<p>Overview Choice experiments estimate individual willingness to pay for a hypothetical good based on its attributes (e.g., a park with or without benches, paths, and lighting). Choice experiments are carried out via survey, which may be in person, or remote via telephone, post, or online. In this way choice experiments can be used to estimate value of change for both users and non-users, although care must be taken that the population of interest have connection to the change being valued.</p> <p>As with the other stated preference methods choice experiments rely on hypothetical choices. In choice experiments participants make repeated choices between hypothetical scenarios, trading off the cost of the alternatives with the descriptive attributes. As a result it can be possible not only to understand the value of the benefit, but also identify which aspect is the “most” valuable in comparison to the others.</p> <p>Quality Choice experiments are well established and used widely across economic valuation, include in appraisal of government intervention. However, because all values are hypothetical care must be taken to interpret values and not over-estimate total value.</p> <p>Resources Significant resources are needed to conduct a choice experiment, including large sample sizes with primary data collection required, and specialised skillsets in scenario design and analysis. Long testing of survey design also means choice experiments typically take a long time to complete.</p> <p>Sensitivity A well designed choice experiment can be highly sensitive to small changes in value, due to the nature of the hypothetical scenario being able to estimate value for different attributes of a site.</p> <p>Transferability Some transfer of values is possible due to the hypothetical nature of the question, however care must be taken to account for different populations between sites.</p>	Transferability	Mid	
	Sensitivity	Mid	
	Predictive or retrospective?	P	
	Quality	Mid	
	Qualitative or quantitative?	Quant	
	Monetary?	Yes	
	Predictive or retrospective Choice experiments only estimate predictive values as they work on hypothetical scenarios only.		
	What is it useful for, and where has it been applied? Choice experiments have been used to measure willingness to pay for reductions in health risks arising from pollutants (Remoundou <i>et al.</i> , 2014), as well as willingness to pay for pollutant removal (Iftekhhar, Polyakov and Rogers, 2022). Linked to health and wellbeing, stress relief and safety arising from characteristics of green spaces have also been assessed through choice experiments (Campagnaro <i>et al.</i> , 2020). Recreation opportunities in green spaces in Scotland have been measured in relation to plants and natural features, and trees in green spaces (Roberts, Glenk and McVittie, 2022), and wildlife in peatlands (Glenk and Martin-Ortega, 2018). Choice experiments have also been used to understand travel preferences for accessing spaces (Small, 2012).		

Regression modelling	Resources: Mid ● ●		
Value of statistical life	Data: Secondary	Time: Mid	Skills: Mid
<p>Overview</p> <p>The value of statistical life refers to standard values placed on quality of life, relative to different injuries or illnesses. This enables different health states to be compared using a common comparator. Changes to the value of statistical life can then be compared to different green and blue space quality, to estimate the benefit arising from green and blue spaces.</p> <p>Values of statistical life include Quality Adjusted Life Years (QALY), Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALY) and Health Adjusted Life Years (HALY).</p>	Transferability	High	
	Sensitivity	Low	
	Predictive or retrospective?	R	
	Quality	Mid	
	Qualitative or quantitative?	Quant	
	Monetary?	Yes	
	Predictive or retrospective	Changes in health can only be reported using value of statistical life after the intervention has been carried out.	
Quality	Studies using value of statistical life use observed data, however, they also rely on correlation, therefore causation cannot be tested.		
Resources	When carrying out large scale regression analysis secondary data is often publicly available (e.g., census data). However, some research may require collection of new primary data, which would significantly increase the time required. Skills required for analysis include regression. At large scales GIS skills may also be required.		
Sensitivity	Due to the large amount of things that impact quality of life, use of the value of statistical life for measuring green and blue space quality are not sensitive, and large changes are needed for change to be detected.		
Transferability	Because statistical life studies are typically carried out at the population level transfer of value is possible, accounting for differences in target population. Values from large scale studies can be applied as a first step in understanding the potential value of smaller scale changes (e.g., development of an individual park), however, further research would be needed to account for the individual character of the area.		
	<p>What is it useful for, and where has it been applied?</p> <p>This method is most suited to changes at the population level, and so suited for large areas, rather than individual green or blue spaces, or parts of spaces. Quality adjusted life years (QALY) have been used often using results from large national level surveys. In England the Health Survey for England measures self-assessed health, and activity within the last 4 weeks. Researchers calculated the amount of physical activity carried out on natural waterbodies, and used standard values to estimate QALY gains (Papathanasopoulou <i>et al.</i>, 2016). A similar study was also carried out for all outdoor activity using the Monitor of Engagement with Natural Environment study (White <i>et al.</i>, 2016).</p>		

Regression modelling	Resources: Mid ●●		
Population modelling	Data: Secondary (public)	Time: Mid	Skills: Mid
<p>Overview Benefits that can be seen at the population level, such as health or social deprivation, can be measured through population statistics. In this method spatial relationships between green and/or blue space and the population statistic are measured, and from this causation assumed. Sources of data can include the census, indices of deprivation (e.g., SIMD), or large scale surveys.</p> <p>Quality National level datasets enable accounting for large numbers of variables and high sample sizes, enabling conclusions to be drawn at the high level. However, as will all regression modelling, the method only works with correlations between outcomes and green or blue spaces, and does not consider causation.</p> <p>Resources Population modelling will generally use secondary data, unless a population level survey is to be commissioned (which would drastically increase time and skills needed). Much of this data is publicly available at a coarse resolution. Fine resolution and some national surveys may require applications and/or payment for use. Skills are needed in handling large datasets and basic statistics.</p> <p>Sensitivity Because population modelling does not target specific users or beneficiaries of green or blue space, it is not sensitive to small changes.</p> <p>Transferability Because models are carried out at large scale results are transferable, as long as difference between populations are accounted for, and spaces are similar. If results are to be applied to smaller scale care should be taken that these are only a starting point, and the individual nature of a space is taken into account.</p>	Transferability	High	
	Sensitivity	Low	
	Predictive or retrospective?	R	
	Quality	Mid	
	Qualitative or quantitative?	Quant	
	Monetary?	No	
	Predictive or retrospective Population modelling looks only at existing interventions, and so can only be used retrospectively.		
	What is it useful for, and where has it been applied? Population modelling should only be used for interventions which could impact large numbers of people, with expected large impacts. In Scotland prescription rates for drugs to treat mental health disorders are available from the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation. Researchers carried out regression analysis between prescription rates and area of green space in Scotland, including covariates from the SIMD and Scottish Census (Roberts, Irvine and McVittie, 2021). To understand impacts on social deprivation area of green space has also been studied in relation to indices of multiple deprivation (Barbosa <i>et al.</i> , 2007) and from community deprivation measures (Cheng, Liao and Zhu, 2021).		

Interviews	Resources: Mid ●●		
Open interviews	Data: Primary	Time: High	Skills: Mid
<p>Overview Open ended interviews involve asking general questions, or providing an opening topic for conversation, and allowing the participant to steer the direction of the interview (although some direction may be provided by the interviewer to remain on topic). Open interviews can be used to understand perceptions or feeling about a space, or to identify things that are important to participants without prior assumptions of importance from researchers. Interview answers are then coded (sorted) by themes to create a narrative across multiple interviews. These themes may be pre-determined by the interviewers, may emerge from the interviews themselves, or may be a combination of the two.</p> <p>Quality Well established method, requires well thought out questions and rigorous analysis.</p> <p>Resources Primary data collection is required, with interview often lasting an hour or more. Interviews must then be transcribed, either in house or sent to a professional transcription service. Analysis is also time consuming.</p> <p>Sensitivity Because interviews are largely related to individual experience, they can be highly sensitive to changes on a small scale, and in a small time period. Although care must be taken not to extrapolate individual experience to the population, open interviews can identify even small changes achieved through green and blue space management.</p> <p>Transferability General themes may be transferable between similar populations and spaces, however, interviews are not necessarily scalable to the population level because they represent individual experiences.</p>	Transferability	Mid	
	Sensitivity	High	
	Predictive or retrospective?	Both	
	Quality	High	
	Qualitative or quantitative?	Qual	
	Monetary?	No	
	Predictive or retrospective	Open interviews can be used both for understanding management that has already occurred, but also for understanding perceptions of potential new changes. Where interviews are used predictively care should be taken to accurately describe the proposed changes.	
	<p>What is it useful for, and where has it been applied? Open interviews can be used to measure almost any benefit arising from green or blue space management. They are likely to be most appropriate when benefits are expected to be highly individual, or where the benefit is potentially unknown to the researcher. Mental wellbeing benefits from interactions with nature were explored using open interviews. Participants found that a nature based experience gave them: a sense of perspective; a mental and emotional sanctuary; and enabled them to be immersed in the moment (Brymer, Crabtree and King, 2021).</p>		

Interviews	Resources: Mid ●		
Semi-structured interviews	Data: Primary	Time: Mid	Skills: Low
<p>Overview Semi-structured interviews include a list of pre-determined questions the interviewer will ask to the participant, directing the conversation. However, some deviation is allowed from the participant, and the interviewer may also ask additional clarifying questions. Analysis involves sorting (coding) of the answers either into pre-determined themes, themes that emerge from the interviews, or a combination of the two.</p> <p>Quality Well established method, requires well thought out questions and rigorous analysis. Quality is likely to be higher for subjects relating to personal experience, rather than experience of others or anticipated experience.</p> <p>Resources Interviews require primary data collection, the conducting, transcription and analysis of which can be time consuming. Designing and conducting of interviews to ensure data collected is accurate and complete must also be done carefully. Both conducting and analysing interview data requires good understanding of the situation at hand. May need specific training to work with specific groups (e.g., children)</p> <p>Sensitivity Interviews can be highly sensitive to small changes, because they focus on individual experience.</p> <p>Transferability Transferable between similar populations and spaces, although the specificity of the interview topic and population may limit other spaces where the results may be relevant. Scaling of responses to the population level should also be avoided, as typically individual data is collected.</p> <p>Predictive or retrospective Interviews can be both predictive and retrospective, however it is likely that retrospective interviews will be more accurate given already experienced change, rather than anticipated change.</p>	Transferability	Mid	
	Sensitivity	High	
	Predictive or retrospective?	Both	
	Quality	High	
	Qualitative or quantitative?	Qual	
	Monetary?	No	
	What is it useful for, and where has it been applied? Semi-structured interviews have a wide application, and are best suited when the benefit being measured is likely to impact people in different ways, have nuance in how it is experienced, or is somewhat unknown. Semi-structured interviews have been used to understand the wide variety of benefits. This has included the physical and mental wellbeing benefits of exercise in blue spaces, as well as the social interaction this enables (Thompson and Wilkie, 2021). And benefits of community gardens (Corrigan, 2011; Furness and Gallaher, 2018). Semi-structured interviews can be particularly useful in understanding benefits for children, or other groups who may not be reached, or be suited to, other methods. Research was carried out with parents of children in coastal communities to understand social interaction (George, Murray and Christian, 2024), as well as to understand play (Miller and Kuhaneck, 2008). Interviews can also be useful to follow change over time, where interviews are repeated at set intervals. This was done to understand changes in activity for over 65-year-olds, with interviews carried out one year apart (Finlay <i>et al.</i> , 2015).		

Interviews	Resources: Mid ●●		
In activity (walking) interviews	Data: Primary	Time: High	Skills: Mid
<p>Overview In-activity (often, but not limited to, while walking) interviews follow the same process as open or semi-structured interviews, however, rather than occurring separate from the environment, interviews take place while moving through the environment. These can be particularly beneficial for understanding green and blue space quality because the participant is able to experience the space throughout the interview.</p>	Transferability		Mid
	Sensitivity		High
	Predictive or retrospective?		Both
	Quality		High
	Qualitative or quantitative?		Qual
	Monetary?		No
	Predictive or retrospective		Interviews are often retrospective, collecting data on current perceptions. However, questions can also be designed to collect data on proposed changes to green and blue spaces, and so be used predictively.
<p>Quality Well established as an effective way to discuss relationship with the landscape. Quality often anticipated to be higher than interviews carried out outwith the space of concern</p>	<p>What is it useful for, and where has it been applied? In-activity interviews are best suited to understanding benefits from single green or blue spaces, or linked spaces that could be visited in one session.</p>		
<p>Resources Interviews are more challenging on the move, and so may therefore take longer, and involve higher skills levels from the researcher than more traditional interviews. The researcher must also be physically able to carry out the activity. Recording equipment will also need to be of higher quality to capture outdoor interviews. Otherwise, resource needs are similar to that of static interviews in transcription and analysis.</p>	<p>Active travel can be well suited to in-activity interviews, and was carried out with working adults and over 65s to understand barriers to participation (Jessiman, Rowe and Jago, 2023). Similar biking interviews have been used to determine how children use their local neighbourhood (Ghekiere et al., 2014).</p>		
<p>Sensitivity In-activity interviews are highly sensitive due to capturing individual experience. Sensitivity may be heightened due to physical presence within the area.</p>	<p>In-activity interviews are highly valuable to understanding how an environment impacts people, because they can answer while experiencing the space first hand. This type of walking interviews were carried out with different types of park users to understand how observing nature impacted different user types in stress reduction in urban environments (Noe and Stolte, 2023).</p>		
<p>Transferability Transferable between similar populations and spaces, although the specificity of the interview topic and population may limit other spaces where the results may be relevant. Scaling of responses to the population level should also be avoided, as typically individual data is collected.</p>			

Interviews	Resources: High ●●●		
Ethnographic interviews	Data: Primary	Time: High	Skills: High
Overview Ethnographic interviews are carried out with organised groups, where researchers are able to join the activity over a prolonged period of time. Interviews typically take place during the activity, and may occur over multiple sessions. They often involve open interviews, although some structure may be given. In addition to the data collected through the interview, the researcher will also use observational data collected through taking part in the activity. Data will be organised into themes (coded) which may emerge from the interviews, or be identified ahead of time by the researcher.	Transferability		Low
	Sensitivity		High
	Predictive or retrospective?		Both
	Quality		High
	Qualitative or quantitative?		Qual
	Monetary?		No
	Predictive or retrospective		Often these interviews will be retrospective, however predictive interviews could also be carried out asking about hypothetical future changes.
Quality Well established for anthropology - although difficult to test in many scenarios and careful design and analysis is needed.	What is it useful for, and where has it been applied? Ethnographic interviews are best suited to single defined spaces, with a regular user-group, whether organised or informal. They are most suited to understanding benefits which are related to how users use the space, and interact with one another.		
Resources Ethnographic interviews have a high time requirement, with prolonged involvement in a group normally required. Interviews are often long, and may take place over multiple sessions, and so transcription and analysis requirements are also high.	Ethnographic interviews were carried out in a woodland setting, where volunteers could come and go as they please to help with the garden and maintenance of the area. Researchers worked alongside the group twice a week for six weeks for participant observation and relationship building. (e.g. motives for attending; feelings about the environment; what participation means to them) and free flowing conversation. Through this method, the researchers were able to spend a lot of time with the participants to build trust and establish the different ways in which engaging in these activities in nature improved their wellbeing (Christie and Cole, 2024).		
Sensitivity Highly sensitive due to the embedded nature of the researchers, and the individual data collected.			
Transferability Limited transferability between populations and spaces, with care that situations are highly similar due to the highly specific nature of the work.			

Reviews	Resources: Mid ●●		
Systematic literature review	Data: Secondary (public)	Time: High	Skills: Mid
<p>Overview Systematic literature reviews use data from existing studies, and use this to draw conclusions that cannot be found by looking at studies in isolation. They take a formalised approach to searching academic and non-academic literature.</p> <p>The PRISMA protocol is a well-established format for structuring and reporting systematic literature reviews. Literature reviews are best suited to questions that have been well researched, and are better applied to larger areas, as results are typically averaged.</p>	Transferability	High	
	Sensitivity	Low	
	Predictive or retrospective?	R	
	Quality	High	
	Qualitative or quantitative?	Both	
	Monetary?	Yes	
	Predictive or retrospective Literature reviews are by definition retrospective. For application to future change see benefit transfer.		
Quality Prisma protocol well established - rigorous inclusion criteria of papers.			
Resources Desk based research using secondary data only, however access to academic papers is required, which may be cost prohibitive outwith an academic institution. Skills are required in understanding and summarising academic literature, and due to the potential volume of literature large amounts of time are needed.	<p>What is it useful for, and where has it been applied? Literature reviews can be applied to study any benefit that has already been well researched and published. They are best suited to larger areas where average values may be applied, or as a starting point for more place-specific research. Reviews have included benefits of blue space use in the elderly (Wang and Md Sani, 2024).</p>		
Sensitivity Likely low, because reviews tend to focus on large trends, and so will not identify smaller or more individual changes.			
Transferability Literature reviews rely on exiting data, and so are transferred by default in this method. Further transfer of data is possible as long as the site matches that of the literature used.			

Reviews	Resources: Low ●		
Benefit transfer	Data: Secondary (public)	Time: Low	Skills: Low
Overview Benefit transfer involves taking results from studies at one site, and applying them at another site. This may be a single site, or may come from multiple additional sites, and may be paired with a literature review.	Transferability		High
	Sensitivity		Low
	Predictive or retrospective?		P
	Quality		High
	Qualitative or quantitative?		Both
	Monetary?		Yes
	Predictive or retrospective		
Quality	Depends on quality of underlying literature, but generally well established. Some detail is lost in transfer, particularly if average values are used.		
Resources	Benefit transfer uses only secondary data, however access may require access to academic literature, which can be cost prohibitive outwith an academic institution. Skills are required to understand limitations of potential for transfer. Time will vary, but could be extensive if used in combination with a literature reviews.		
Sensitivity	Likely low, because reviews tend to focus on large trends, and so will not identify smaller or more individual changes.		
Transferability	By default benefit transfer involves transfer of values between sites. Additional transferability of results must take account of the similarity between sites.		
		What is it useful for, and where has it been applied? Benefit transfer studies are suited to benefits that are well established and common across multiple sites. They are often used in health studies, including a review of literature to identify association between built environment and physical activity (Zapata-Diomedes, Herrera and Veerman, 2016).	

Surveys	Resources: Low ●		
Health self-report	Data: Primary	Time: Low	Skills: Low
<p>Overview Surveys based on self-reported health may use single questions or standardised scales to link health to green or blue space characteristics, either measured or reported. Such surveys can be carried out with specific populations before and after changes have been made, or alternatively conducted over larger areas, where access to different spaces can be used as a proxy for intervention.</p> <p>Many standardised health scales exist to measure various aspects of physical and mental health. Anxiety and depression measured through GHQ-12, while K-10 measures psychological distress.</p>	Transferability	Mid	
	Sensitivity	Low	
	Predictive or retrospective?	R	
	Quality	Mid	
	Qualitative or quantitative?	Quant	
	Monetary?	No	
	Predictive or retrospective Typically retrospective. Hypothetical health changes could be measured, however this would be hard to test the robustness of the data.		
Quality Standardised measure of mental health well tested, however self-reported health is open to error in understanding from participants. Correlative studies only, causation is not tested.	What is it useful for, and where has it been applied? Health self-report surveys are suitable only for measuring the health benefit of green or blue space. They can be applied to spaces over a wide range of scales, and are particularly useful for monitoring targeted interventions with a specific group. Yin <i>et al.</i> (2023) used psychological scales to understand the importance of water in the benefits of outdoor exposure.		
Resources Primary data collections is required, however the extent of the survey is flexible, and so could be relatively low resource if a small population is targeted. Analysis can also be straightforward, particularly for before-after intervention studies. Where secondary GIS data is included, or national level surveys, expertise required will increase.			
Sensitivity Due to the complex nature of health, sensitivity of health scales to changes in green and blue space quality will be low.	Health statistics can also be used from national level surveys. Nutsford <i>et al.</i> , (2016) used data from a national level survey implementing the K10 scale of psychological distress to understand impacts of blue and green space availability and visibility.		
Transferability Studies which cover a large population will have higher transferability than those which focus on a single population, which require careful matching of sites.			

Surveys	Resources: Mid ●●		
Qualitative surveys	Data: Primary	Time: Mid	Skills: Mid
Overview Qualitative surveys use open ended questions to collect data. These can be administered in person, or remotely through postal, online or telephone. Analysis similar to interviews, in identifying themes between answers, either defined by the researcher or arising from the data.	Transferability		Mid
	Sensitivity		High
	Predictive or retrospective?		Both
	Quality		High
	Qualitative or quantitative?		Qual
	Monetary?		No
	Predictive or retrospective		Most likely to be retrospective, however questions can be framed to understand preferences for proposed future changes.
Quality	Well established method, although questions will matter.		
Resources	Primary data collection, requiring careful determination of questions and analysis. Time variable depending on scale of survey.		
Sensitivity	Due to the individual nature of the answers sensitivity can be high, depending on the framing of the question.		
Transferability	Transferable between similar populations and spaces. Similarity between sites and populations is important to note, particularly for individual experiences rather than generalisable statements.		
	What is it useful for, and where has it been applied? Similar to qualitative interviews, qualitative surveys are suited to understanding benefits when little is known about the benefit, when you are interested in a deeper understanding of how the benefit is perceived by those receiving it. Qualitative surveys can be used across a range of benefits and spaces. Völker, Matros and Claßen (2016) used qualitative interviews to examine inter-relationships between blue spaces and health-related appropriate processes. Participants noted that they used the blue spaces for physical activity, as well as quiet activities - both of which improved health overall.		

Surveys	Resources: Low ●		
Multiple choice surveys	Data: Primary	Time: Low	Skills: Low
Overview Multiple choice interviews can include question types such as binary choice (yes/no), Likert scale (e.g., Strongly Agree, to Strongly Disagree) or lists of answers with options for single or multiple selections. In this way quantitative answers to specific questions can be understood. This may include standardised scales.	Transferability		High
	Sensitivity		Mid
	Predictive or retrospective?		Both
	Quality		Mid
	Qualitative or quantitative?		Quant
	Monetary?		No
	Predictive or retrospective		Both, questions can be framed around existing sites, or planned changes.
Quality	Depends on specific questions, but well established.		
Resources	Primary data collection, though sample sizes may be small if specific areas are to be studied. Some statistical knowledge needed for analysis.		
Sensitivity	Could be high, depending on the questions asked. Limitations will arise due to the restricted nature of the answers to pre-determined categories.		
Transferability	Depends significantly on the questions asked. Typically, transferable between similar spaces and populations.		
What is it useful for, and where has it been applied?		Quantitative surveys are useful to answer questions with a limited number of possible answers. They are particularly valuable to get a large sample size to cover a large population. Quantitative surveys are widely used, including with tourists (Terkenli <i>et al.</i> , 2020), to understand how spaces facilitate socialisation (Rugel <i>et al.</i> , 2019; Swapan, Bay and Marinova, 2019)c, or perceived safety of spaces (Hong <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Evensen, Hemsett and Nordh, 2021).	

Surveys	Resources: Mid ●●		
Diary	Data: Primary	Time: High	Skills: Mid
<p>Overview</p> <p>Diary based studies are a long-term survey type method, where participants report activities over long periods of time, potentially months to years. Diaries can cover qualitative and quantitative data, although qualitative data requires much higher resources to analyse. Contents of diaries should be well defined and linked to something of high importance to participants to maintain responses through the whole study period.</p>	Transferability		Mid
	Sensitivity		High
	Predictive or retrospective?		R
	Quality		High
	Qualitative or quantitative?		Both
	Monetary?		No
	Predictive or retrospective		Retrospective as recording existing data in real time.
<p>Quality</p> <p>Direct records, so as long as volunteers are careful in their recording data should be of high quality. Does somewhat rely on self-record so potential for exaggeration.</p>	<p>What is it useful for, and where has it been applied?</p> <p>Diaries are useful to understand how an individual's relationship with a space or activity may change over time, or in relation to other factors such as season, or other demands on time. Due to the long commitment required from participants best results will be likely for questions which relate to things that are of high importance to participants. Diaries have been used to measure home grown food production, where volunteers recorded weight of all fruit and vegetables acquired over a week, including brought, gifted and homegrown over one year (Gulyas and Edmondson, 2024). Other examples include recording of active travel, sometimes linked to GPS tracking (De Geus <i>et al.</i>, 2007; Ogilvie <i>et al.</i>, 2008; Ta <i>et al.</i>, 2021).</p>		
<p>Resources</p> <p>Primary data collection, with relatively straightforward method, however significant resources required to keep up with respondents over long time periods. Analysis can be simple as tracking through time. If combined with GPS trackers higher skill set needed.</p>			
<p>Sensitivity</p> <p>Potential to be highly sensitive to change on an individual level.</p>			
<p>Transferability</p> <p>Relies on the subject being studied, and transfer to highly similar locations.</p>			

Focus groups	Resources: Mid ●●		
Focus groups	Data: Primary	Time: Low	Skills: Mid
Overview Focus groups collect data from a group of respondents at the same time, enabling them to discuss and bounce off one another. to Groups are often made up of individuals already somewhat known to each other, although alternative groups made up of intentionally diverse individuals may be used for specific questions.	Transferability		Mid
	Sensitivity		High
	Predictive or retrospective?		Both
	Quality		High
	Qualitative or quantitative?		Qual
	Monetary?		No
	Predictive or retrospective		Both, depending on questions posed. Often used to discuss future changes.
Quality Focus groups are well established, though participants must be carefully selected and managed	What is it useful for, and where has it been applied? Focus groups are a good method to collect information that is non-contentious, and that may benefit from group deliberation. They are typically used to discuss a single, or local group of spaces, although can also be used to assess national level green and blue spaces, with the appropriate participants. Focus groups may be used with those with decision making or management roles, such as research carried out on perceived safety with park managers (Evensen, Hemsett and Nordh, 2021). Users may also take part in focus groups, including users of cemeteries (Swensen and Skår, 2019), and teenagers (Simons <i>et al.</i> , 2013) or over 65's using active travel (Jessiman, Rowe and Jago, 2023).		
Resources Primary data is collected through focus groups. Focus groups can require multiple facilitators and a higher level of skill than interviews due to the larger size and group dynamics.			
Sensitivity Can be highly sensitive to changes depending on questions asked and make up of focus group.			
Transferability Focus groups are often specific to sites, and so careful matching of sites and populations may be needed. Higher transferability would be possible for groups focusing on wider issues.			

Observation	Resources: Mid ●●		
Observation	Data: Primary	Time: High	Skills: Low
Overview Observation techniques include watching a specific area for a set period of time, recording observation, typically categorised into a set list. Observation can be a good method to understand how people are using a space, and is often combined with other methods.	Transferability		Low
	Sensitivity		Mid
	Predictive or retrospective?		R
	Quality		Mid
	Qualitative or quantitative?		Quant
	Monetary?		No
	Predictive or retrospective		
Quality Tested systematic methods, depending on the framework used. However, the method relies on only observation, and therefore infers causation from correlation.	What is it useful for, and where has it been applied? Observation studies are useful for understanding single sites, or parts of an area. Alone they can answer only questions about activity, and cannot provide explanation. Observation has been used to record play intensity for children (McKenzie <i>et al.</i> , 2020), and map the way that people use public spaces (Askarizad and Safari, 2020). The method can also be applied to understand how people interaction, such as social interaction (Chen <i>et al.</i> , 2024).		
Resources Direct observation does not require significant training, however this may increase depending on analysis carried out, GIS and modelling skills could be required.			
Sensitivity Sensitivity has potential to be high, however, in the context of green and blue spaces it is likely that other factors obscure impacts.			
Transferability Not very transferable, though may highlight which types of areas that might encourage activity in other areas.			

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4 Appendix 1: Definitions of method details

	Definition	Levels
Method	Method name as listed in the “benefits” table.	NA
Method details	Overview of method. Full details found in appendix.	NA
Transferability	Potential for results of the method estimated in one location to be applicable in a different location.	<u>High</u> – Results can be easily transferred, although in all cases care must be taken to account for similarities between locations. <u>Mid</u> – Results could be transferred, however some re-analysis may be required to account for the differences between locations. <u>Low</u> – It is rare that results can be transferred between locations, and caution should be used when applying expectations from one location to another.

<p>Resources</p>	<p>Amount of resources needed to carry out the method. Given that in some cases this may vary, we have estimated according to the minimum resources required.</p> <p>Resources organised into data required, time required, and skills of those carrying out the work.</p>	<p><u>Data Required:</u> <u>Data – Primary</u> – Primary data collection will need to be carried out (i.e., new data will need to be collected). <u>Data – Secondary (public)</u> – Secondary data is likely to be publicly available. <u>Data – Secondary (private)</u> – Secondary data is likely to be available, however it is unlikely to be publicly accessible, and application and/or payment to access the data may be required.</p> <p><u>Time Required:</u> <u>Time – High</u> – Carrying out this research will take sustained effort over months to years to complete. <u>Time – Mid</u> – Carrying out this research will require either sustained effort over weeks to months, or sporadic effort (e.g., half a day every 3 months) over a longer time period. <u>Time – Low</u> – Only a small amount of time will be needed to complete this research, with completion expected in under one month.</p> <p><u>Skills Required:</u> <u>Skills – High</u> – The method requires specialised training, and would most likely be carried out by a team at a research institute or university. <u>Skills – Mid</u> – Some specialised skills are needed, but could be undertaken in-house with training. <u>Skills – Low</u> – Minimal specialised skills or training needed for this method.</p>
<p>Sensitivity</p>	<p>Ability of the method to detect small changes in quality. A more sensitive method will detect changes more quickly, or changes that happen on a smaller scale.</p>	<p><u>High</u> – Changes can be detected immediately following a change to a space, or can be detected over an area 10s of metres square. <u>Mid</u> – Changes can be detected months to a year after the change, or over a mid-size area up to 100m². <u>Low</u> – Change can only be detected years after a change to a space, or where the change occurs over large areas.</p>
<p>Predictive or retrospective?</p>	<p>Can the method be applied before a change is made to a space, to forecast what the impact of change may be (predictive) or is it applied afterwards to measure the impact of a change?</p>	<p><u>Predictive</u> – The method can only be applied to forecast the impacts of a change in the future. <u>Retrospective</u> – The method can only be applied to measure the impacts of changes already made. <u>Both</u> – The method can be used to predict future change, or to measure impacts of past change.</p>

Quality	Although all methods presented in this toolkit are considered to produce robust results, the quality may vary from the “gold standard” methods to those more readily applied.	<p><u>High</u> – Methods considered “gold standard” within their field, typically relying on observed data.</p> <p><u>Mid</u> – Well established methods within their field, however limitations of the data should be recognised.</p> <p><u>Low</u> – Robust methods, however may only indicate large trends, or other methods may be available which provide more detailed information.</p>
Qual/ Quant	Methods may report numerical data, or data based on text, such as outcomes from interview or workshops. Some methods may report both types of data.	<p><u>Qual</u> – The method reports only non-numerical data (qualitative data).</p> <p><u>Quant</u> – The method reports only numerical data (quantitative data).</p> <p><u>Mixed</u> – Both numerical and non-numerical data are reported.</p>
£	Monetary methods report, or can report, outcomes in monetary terms (e.g., costs, value).	<p><u>Yes</u> – Monetary estimates can be made.</p> <p><u>No</u> – No monetary estimates can be made using this method alone (other methods may be employed to estimate monetary values of results in some cases).</p>
Page	Further details of the method can be found by following the page link.	NA